

SOCIAL MATRIX OF POSTWAR PERIOD IN THE REPUBLIC OF AZERBAIJAN

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Summary. *The social matrix of the two postwar periods in the Republic of Azerbaijan is given which can serve as a beacon for the mechanisms of action to be directed in the restoration and reconstruction work in the coming years. According to the results of the social matrix of the postwar periods in the Republic of Azerbaijan it is possible to say that damage was caused to residential and non-residential areas within the categories. These are losses that no matter how much we can compensate will always remain a deep void.*

Keywords: *Republic of Azerbaijan, social, postwar, mathematical, matrix.*

СОЦИАЛЬНАЯ МАТРИЦА ПОСЛЕВОЕННОГО ПЕРИОДА В АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНСКОЙ РЕСПУБЛИКЕ

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Резюме. *Представлена социальная матрица двух послевоенных периодов в Азербайджанской Республике, которая может служить ориентиром для механизмов действий, которые необходимо направить в восстановительные и реконструкционные работы в ближайшие годы. По результатам анализа социальной матрицы послевоенных периодов в Азербайджанской Республике можно сказать, что ущерб был нанесен жилым и нежилым районам в рамках следующих категорий. Это потери, которые, как бы мы ни старались их компенсировать, всегда будут оставаться глубокой пустотой.*

Methods: *Retrospective and comparative analysis, statistical analysis.*

Scientific innovation: *In the research work the social matrix of the I and II Garabakh wars in the Republic of Azerbaijan was extracted for the first time. Obtaining the matrix is one of the mathematical methods found within the framework of technical sciences. In this regard, the precise expression of the changes in the social environment in numbers guided by the multidisciplinary approach of the mathematical method gives a strong impetus to the scientific innovation of the research work.*

INTRODUCTION

Currently, social control which is an element of social policy has gained superiority through statistical indicators formed from numbers, equivalent to the regularity of the digital world. In this research work the social matrix of the two postwar periods in the Republic of Azerbaijan is given which can serve as a beacon for the mechanisms of action to be directed in the restoration and reconstruction work in the coming years. This research work can be used in the compilation of statistical data or in the study and strengthening of the social policy of the Republic of Azerbaijan.

Social matrix of postwar period in the Republic of Azerbaijan

The following directions were taken into account for the construction of the social matrix of the postwar period in the Republic of Azerbaijan:

- 1.Number of people killed and martyred
- 2.Injured and disabled
- 3.Agricultural damage

- 4.Damaged vehicles
- 5.Damaged residential and non-residential areas

	1	2	3	4	5
IP	20.000	50.000	6.000	2830	201.596

	1	2	3	4	5
IIP	2876	454	1018	346	13360

If we assume the single matrix of losses in the social sphere of the Republic of Azerbaijan in both postwar periods using the following mathematical method:

$$Tr = IP + IIP$$

We can write the matrix of the overall result.

	1	2	3	4	5
Tr	22.876	50.454	7.018	3.176	214.956

CONCLUSION

According to the results of the social matrix of the postwar periods in the Republic of Azerbaijan it is possible to say that damage was caused to residential and non-residential areas within the categories. In total there were 280.426 losses in IP and 18.054 losses in IIP in all five categories.

It is possible to say with certainty that the period of the heaviest and highest losses in material and psychological terms is the first postwar period. This is a loss that no matter how much we can compensate will always remain a deep void.

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